

by exposing them to iodine vapours. Alongside the authentic sample of the coupled product of sulphadiazole, the solution of the diazotised sulphadiazole in acetone ($10^{-6}M$) was spotted and at the same position a solution of acetylacetone (equivalent 1.0 mol of sulphadiazole) in acetone was also applied. Both the samples came in sequence and gave similar R_f values.

Results and Discussion

When the sulphadiazole drugs were spotted as mixtures or individually and were then converted on the plates into their coupled products with acetylacetone, on subsequent irrigation, they were distinctly resolved. Thus a mixture of nine sulphadiazole drugs in the form of their coupled products was readily resolved and their sequence on silica gel-G plate was as follows: sulphadiazole < sulphadiazamide < phthalylsulphathiazole < sulphadiazimidine < sulphamethizole < sulphosomidine < sulphathiazole < metacalfin < sulphamethoxazole.

The best solvent system was found to be dichloromethane-carbon tetrachloride-methanol (45 : 50 : 5, v/v) and the best adsorbent system being silica gel-G impregnated with 20% $CaCO_3$ and 1% tetrabutylammonium bromide. In these systems all the nine coupled products of sulphadiazole drugs could be separated. Their sequence on the developed chromatogram was as follows: sulphadiazole ($R_f=0.12$) < phthalylsulphathiazole (0.28) < sulphadiazamide (0.40) < sulphasomidine (0.50) < sulphamethizole (0.62) < metacalfin (0.78) < sulphadiazimidine (0.86) < sulphamethoxazole (0.93) < sulphathiazole (0.99). In all these cases coupled products could be observed directly as yellow spots and there was no necessity for a spray reagent as in case of sulphadiazole drugs alone.

On the other hand, good separation could not be achieved using silica gel-G impregnated with Triton-X 100, sodium lauryl sulphate and cupric acetate (with or without 20% $CaCO_3$)—either there was no clear separation or profuse tailing occurred with the majority of the drugs. Mixtures of polar solvents when employed for irrigation of plates resulted in either long tailing or highly diffused spots. Non-polar solvents and their mixtures produced excellent resolution of compounds. Thin coatings (0.5 mm) of the adsorbents produced good results. In general, it was observed that mobility of compounds on silica gel-G impregnated with 1% tetrabutylammonium bromide was greatly increased when compared with silica gel-G or silica gel-G+20% $CaCO_3$.

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On Line Electrochemical Determination of Ascorbic Acid

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THERE is a great interest in improving assay procedure for vitamin-C. Presence of electrochemically oxidisable 'enediol' group in ascorbic acid makes it analysable by anodic voltammetry. Various electrochemical methods for determination of ascorbic acid have been reported¹. In the present study we report a simple, fast and sensitive method for the determination of ascorbic acid by high performance liquid chromatography (hplc) with electrochemical detection at glassy carbon electrode (GCE).

Experimental

Differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) and cyclic voltammetric (CV) studies were made on BAS-100 electrochemical analyzer in conjunction with a DMP-40 series digital plotter. GCE served as working electrode and Ag/AgCl as reference electrode. A Gilson-HPLC unit with chromatofield electrochemical detector was used for liquid chromatographic determinations. Chromatographic

conditions were as follows: A Partisil 5 ODS-3, C-18 5 μm , 4.6 $\times$ 250 mm column with a CO ; PELL ODS guard column (Whatman), mobile phase-methanol (Lichrosolve grade Merck) containing 2 g dm⁻³ KNO₃ was run at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. In electrochemical detector, the working electrode and reference electrode were GCE and Ag/AgCl respectively. Detector potential was set at 400 mV.

A fresh solution of ascorbic acid (A.R.) was prepared in deoxygenated double-distilled water to inhibit autooxidation. Britton-Robinson (B.R.) buffer was used to maintain the pH and a 0.2 M lithium chloride solution was used as supporting electrolyte in DPV experiments. A commercial multivitamin preparation, Sorvicia (East India Pharmaceutical Works Ltd., Calcutta) was used for assaying purpose. The fine powder of the tablet was dispersed in minimum amount of deoxygenated double-distilled water with vigorous shaking and made upto 10 ml stock solution followed by quantitative dilution with mobile phase to yield a nominal 1–4 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of ascorbic acid solution.

Results and Discussion

DPP studies of ascorbic acid at dropping mercury electrode (DME) indicated a well-defined single oxidation peak in acidic solutions². Though peak height increased with increasing acidity but at lower pH anodic limit of DME did not permit a well-defined DP peak. Therefore GCE was chosen as working electrode where it displayed a sharp DP peak at +0.25 V in a medium of pH 3.0. The increase in peak current with concentration was found to be linear in the concentration range of 1–400 ppm.

Keeping in view of DPV observations at GCE, HPLC-technique was employed with an electrochemical detector for sub-micro level determinations. The suitable potential was chosen by recording a cyclic voltammogram of ascorbic acid at pH 3.0. It revealed single anodic peak at +0.310 V, thus electrochemical detector was set at +400 mV. The lowest detection limit was found to be 0.5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. A minimum one microlitre injection could be easily assayed. Retention time was found to be 3.4 min offering a rapid determination. The method was applied for the analysis of

vitamin-C contents in commercial tablet preparation. Quantitation was done by standard addition method. The observations with precision and accuracy are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1 – PRECISION AND ACCURACY OF ASCORBIC ACID DETERMINATION

Smple	Vit -C present	Vit.-C determined*	Standarda deviation (±)	Recovery %
Standard	600 ng ml ⁻¹	596.60 ng ml ⁻¹	6.9	99.4
Commercial multivitamin preparation	500 mg	497.58 mg	7.4	99.5

*Mean of five determinations.

The existing conventional methods³ for ascorbic acid estimation lack high specificity and sensitivity. Volumetric method with 2,6-dichloroindophenol is applicable only in absence of ferrous, stannous, cuprous, sulphite etc., and fluorometric method is an indirect method involving a number of steps. Comparatively electrochemical assay is found to be more specific, sensitive and requires fewer steps in sample preparation as well as in determinations. Furthermore, hplc with electrochemical detection offers a relatively simple and fast method for determination of ascorbic acid specially for those samples where only few microlitre of sample is available.

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